

Analytical Applications of Thiosalicylidene Ethylenediimine Part I. Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt(II)*

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Manuscript received 31 January 1974; accepted 23 May 1974

A sensitive spectrophotometric method for determination of Co(II) with thiosalicylidene ethylenediimine (Thiosalen) has been developed. Beer's law is obeyed in the range of 0.25-6.0 μg of cobalt, per ml, at pH 8.2 in aqueous-acetone medium. The sensitivity is 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, and the molar extinction coefficient at 470 nm is 6934.

REACTIONS of thiosalicylidene ethylenediimine (Thiosalen) (I) with metal ions have been reported by Beck¹. However, potentialities of

this reagent for its analytical uses have not been explored. In this work the reaction between Thiosalen and Co(II) has been used for spectrophotometric determination of cobalt.

Experimental

A Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements, and pH measurements were made on Elico pH meter L1 10.

Thiosalen was prepared by the method of Beck¹. *o*-Chlorobenzaldehyde was treated with ethylenediimine to obtain bis-*o*-chlorobenzilidene ethylenediimine (m.p. 78°) 7.6 g. of this Schiff's base were treated with NaHS in ethanol and thiosalicylidene ethylenediimine formed was extracted with CHCl_3 and the solution was made upto 100 ml with CHCl_3 . The reagent solution was stored in a sealed container between uses as it is slowly oxidized by air. It was standardized by titration with standard lead tetraacetate solution in acetic acid using quinalizarin indicator according to the method recommended by Verma and Bose² for mercaptans. A concentrated solution was used for analytical work to keep CHCl_3 content to a minimum.

A.R. grade chemicals were used throughout. All aqueous solutions were prepared in deionized water.

The stock solution of cobalt was prepared from cobalt nitrate or chloride and was analysed for cobalt by EDTA method³ and pyridine-thiocyanate method³. Acetone and chloroform were used after purification.

Results and Discussion

Absorption Spectra

Absorption spectrum (fig. 1) of Thiosalen at pH 8.2 in 75% acetone medium shows a peak at 330 nm

Fig. 1. Adsorption spectra of Co(II):Thiosalen complex
A. Co(II) Complex vs. reagent blank
Co(II) = $2.545 \times 10^{-3} M$, at pH = 8.2
B. Thiosalen at pH 8.2.

(not shown in fig.) and a shoulder near 420 nm. The spectral curve for Co(II) complex against reagent blank indicates a maximum at 380-390 nm ($\epsilon = 25,934 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and another at 470 nm ($\epsilon = 6,904 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The latter wavelength was chosen for the analytical work and absorbance

* Paper read at the Annual Convention of Chemists, held at Calcutta, December, 1973.

of the complex was measured against an appropriate reagent blank.

Effect of pH :

Fig. 2 shows the absorption spectra of Co(II) complex at different pH values in the pH range

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of Co(II) Complex at different pH Co(II) = $2.545 \times 10^{-5} M$.

- A pH 7.3
- B pH 7.8
- C pH 7.9-8.2
- D pH 8.6
- E pH 9.0
- F pH 10.1

7.1-10.1. It may be seen that the nature of all these spectra is very similar, suggesting formation a single complex species in this pH range. The absorption of the solution is maximum and constant in the pH range 7.9-8.2. Accordingly all analytical work was carried out at pH of 8.2 adjusted with saturated solution of sodium acetate.

Effect of time and temperature :

Development of the full colour intensity of the Co(II) complex solution takes less than 15 min and the colour is stable for 1 hr. All absorbance measurements were made 15 mins after mixing of the solutions.

There is no change in the absorbance of the solution in the temperature range of 15° - 38° . The colour fades beyond 38° .

Procedure for determination of Cobalt :

To a suitable aliquot (< 2.0 ml.) of solution containing 2.5-60 μg . of cobalt, added 0.5 ml of Thiosalen solution of CHCl_3 followed by enough saturated solution of sodium acetate to give a pH of 8.2. Added sufficient water and acetone to give a final volume of 10.0 ml. containing 75% acetone (v/v). Mixed and kept for 15 mins. Measured the absorbance at 470 nm against a reagent blank prepared, in the same way but without Co(II) solution.

Conformity of Beer's Law :

The brown-red coloured Co(II) complex adheres to Beer's law in the concentration range of 0.25-6.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. of cobalt at 470 nm.

Precision and Accuracy :

Precision and accuracy of the spectrophotometric method were tested by analysing samples containing known amounts of cobalt. With solutions containing 1.5 μg of cobalt per ml, the standard deviation was 0.022 and the average of ten determinations was 1.50 ± 0.04 μg per ml at 95% confidence limit.

Sensitivity :

The sensitivity of the spectrophotometric method for determination of Co(II) according to Sandell's⁴ definition is 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and molar absorptivity of the coloured species at 470 nm is 6094 evaluated on the basis of total cobalt.

Interferences studies :

F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , SO_3^{2-} , SO_4^{2-} , NO_2^- , NO_3^- and acetate do not interfere in the determination of cobalt. CN^- , SCN^- , S^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, EDTA., citrate and tartrate interfere. Among cations alkali, metals, alkaline earth, Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , V^{5+} do not interfere. Ni^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Mo^{6+} and W^{6+} interfere seriously as they form complexes with Thiosalen. Further interference studies are in progress.

Thus Thiosalene affords as a sensitive but not very selective spectrophotometric method for determination of cobalt.

References

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